

Powering of Wireless Sensors through the Exclusive use of Kinetic Energy

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Abstract—This paper demonstrates the powering of wireless sensor nodes with the exclusive use of a novel kinetic energy harvester (KEH). This KEH is designed to operate under low accelerations which are practical to find in a typical environment where a sensor would be deployed. Four different sensor types were powered with accelerations ranging between 17-300mg.

I. INTRODUCTION

With sensors being used in all types of environments, including the hard to get to and hazardous, coupled with the cost of replacing batteries, it is desirable for sensors to be self-powered using continuous environmental sources. It has been estimated that as many as 90% of Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) applications cannot be realized without the use of energy harvesting devices to supply self-sustaining power, [1]. Existing kinetic energy harvesters (KEH) rely on specific sources that contain high vibration levels [2], [3]. Example sources that typical KEH utilize include pumps, HVAC vents, or various appliances [4]. Because not all environments contain high vibration sources, it is necessary to design KEHs that do not rely on them. Through measurements at Space and Naval Warfare System Center Pacific (SSC Pacific) and other sources, we have found that vibration acceleration peaks found in usable structures are less than 0.3 g (where $1 \text{ g} = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$) and are typically 10's of mg or less.

SSC Pacific has successfully developed kinetic energy harvesting devices using a novel patented design [5]. These devices have demonstrated the ability to exclusively power various wireless sensors. Sensors that have been powered are the Texas Instrument MSP430 EZ430-RF2500, a Crossbow Wireless Mote, and the MicroStrain Wireless strain gauge and tri-axial accelerometer nodes, using accelerations between 17-290mg rms. This device design efficiently extracts power from low ambient vibrations in the environment of the sensor with the use of a spring mass system that oscillates two like-pole facing magnets about a coil contained within the flux gap. Between transmissions, the KEH continuously builds up charge in a storage element until the wireless sensor is ready to transmit during its next transmission cycle.

II. DEVICE DESIGN

The KEH device developed by SSC PACIFIC is shown in Figure 1. A cross sectional view of the KEH, with references to all of the variable parameters is in Figure 2. The two magnets are rigidly attached with like poles facing each other.

This condenses the magnetic field lines such that there is a large magnetic field gradient between the magnets. A coil rests between the two magnets such that small displacements will cause the coil to travel through a large magnetic field gradient. With this system either the magnets or the coil can be the oscillating spring mass system, while the other is stationary.

The device used to power the sensors mentioned contains N52 magnets with a 5.875 mm diameter and a thickness of 6.35 mm. The coil has an 18 mm outer diameter, a 1.6 mm inner diameter, and a thickness of 2.7 mm. The coil resistance is 20.5 k Ω . The resonant frequency of the KEH was 18.6 Hz for the TI MSP430 and 42 Hz for the other harvesters. The total diameter of the device is 34 mm, with a height of 30 mm; therefore the total volume is 27 cm³. The total mass of the device is 36.5 grams.

Figure 1. SSC PACIFIC KEH device, mass = 36.5 grams, volume = 27 cm³. The metal springs are visible on top

Figure 2. (Top) EH design with magnetic flux lines. (Bottom) EH dimensions: O.D. = coil outer diameter, I.D. = coil inner diameter, T = coil thickness, H = magnet thickness, G = magnet separation, D = magnet diameter

III. SETUP

The KEH is provided with a vibration source by using a Labworks Inc. ET-139 electrodynamic shaker. An accelerometer is attached to the shaker to monitor the applied acceleration amplitude and frequency. The shaker is driven by a signal from an LDC Photon II module. The module both provides a control signal to the shaker, and reads the accelerometer signal and harvester output via a two-channel ADC. All the data is displayed in real-time on a laptop screen. The frequency of the shaker is tuned via software control to match the KEH resonance. The vibration amplitude is adjusted to the minimum amount required for sustained transmissions. The transmitted sensor data from the modules is received by a base station module, which displays the sensor readings in real-time on the laptop via USB. A simple diagram of the test setup is shown in Figure 3.

A passive full wave rectifier, comprised of Schottky diodes is used to convert the AC Voltage output of the KEH to DC, which is then applied to a storage capacitor (220 μ F for the TI and MicroStrain transmitters and 9.1 mF for the Crossbow transmitter). The diodes were chosen to have low leakage, low on-resistance, and very low forward voltage drop (0.375 V). The capacitor is a low-leakage tantalum or ceramic type, and electrolytic for the Crossbow node. The storage capacitor charges up during the sleep mode of the TI and MicroStrain transmitters, and then releases the stored power required during transmissions. At low transmission rates more time is available for the capacitor to charge up, and allows transmission at lower average acceleration levels. The Crossbow transmitter uses the most power because it does not have an efficient sleep mode and draws a significant amount of continuous power. The capacitor size must be tailored to the amount of energy needed for a particular transmitter to make a transmission. It must be large enough to store enough energy such that the voltage across the capacitor does not drop below the minimum voltage required to power the transmitter during discharge. A battery-type storage element may alternatively be used, but would require extra power for under/over-voltage protection circuitry.

Figure 3. Outline of driving the energy harvester, rectifying the power, and powering the sensor

IV. SENSORS

The wireless sensors that have been powered and will be discussed in this article are the TI MSP430 eZ430-RF2500T temperature and voltage gauge, MicroStrain 3-axis Accelerometer, MicroStrain Strain Gauge, and the Crossbow MICA2, as shown in Figure 4. The TI MSP430 contains a temperature gauge, voltage monitor, and powers two LEDs, and contains a CC2500 2.4 GHz multi-channel RF transceiver. The MicroStrain Accelerometer is a 3-axis accelerometer that, as with the MicroStrain strain gauge, uses a 2.4 GHz RF transceiver. The Crossbow measures temperature, pressure, light intensity and has a 2-axis accelerometer. It uses a MPR400CB processor board and transmits at 868 MHz. The transmission profiles of these sensors are shown in Figure 5. The TI MSP430 sensor and the MicroStrain sensors transmit every 5 seconds, while the Crossbow sensor transmits once a minute. The average power consumption of the TI, MicroStrain Accelerometer, MicroStrain Strain Gauge, and Crossbow are 60 μ W, 0.3 mW, 0.3 mW, and 1 mW, respectively.

More specifically, the TI MSP430 uses 0.286 mJ per transmission, which lasts 4.68 ms and a sleep energy of 4.17 μ J. The MicroStrain accelerometer uses 0.246 mJ per transmission with a transmission time of 5.05 ms and 0.573 mJ during sleep mode. The MicroStrain strain gauge requires 0.3187 mJ per transmission for 7.7 ms, with sleep energy of 0.355 mJ.

Figure 6 shows the power usage during the periods in which the sensors are not transmitting. During this phase the KEH charges the storage capacitor to supply enough power for transmission. The Crossbow sensor (top right) consumes more power than the other sensors (note, the scale on the y-axis is higher than the other plots) due to the fact that this sensor continually tries to communicate with a network of other sensors in a meshed network, rather than simply collecting and sending data.

Figure 4. Clockwise, starting at top left, TI MSP430 temperature node, Crossbow MICA2 multi-sensor node, MicroStrain 3-axis accelerometer, MicroStrain strain gauge

Figure 5. Transmission plots, power verse time for (clockwise starting at top left), TI MSP430, Crossbow MICA2, MicroStrain Accelerometer, and MicroStrain Strain Gauge

Figure 6. Power consumption during non-transmission for (clockwise starting at top left), TI MSP430, Crossbow MICA2, MicroStrain Accelerometer, and MicroStrain Strain Gauge

V. RESULTS

All of the sensors were successfully powered exclusively and continuously using the KEH described. The recorded acceleration levels were the minimum single frequency accelerations that were used to power the sensors with a set transmission period. The acceleration could easily be decreased given larger transmission periods to allow for a longer charging time. In addition, the input accelerations at a single frequency used to power the KEH are not representative vibration spectra in a typical environment. Instead there are often lower amplitude peaks at nearby frequencies that are captured by the harvester to increase the overall power production (although not as efficiently as the designed frequency). An example of a vibration spectrum is shown in Figure 7 and an example frequency response of

a harvester is shown in Figure 8. As can be seen in the frequency response, as the vibrational amplitude increases, the harvester's band width expands, allowing for more frequencies to be captured.

Figure 7. An example of a vibration spectrum for a given source

Figure 8. Frequency sweep of a KEH at four different accelerations, 1 mg, 2 mg, 5 mg, and 10 mg

The TI MSP430 was powered at 17 mg at 17.6 Hz, with a transmission every 5 seconds. The TI MSP430 is able to transfer about 10 meters. The capacitor charge and discharge is shown in Figure 9. The MicroStrain Strain Gauge was operated using an acceleration of 103 mg at 42 Hz with a transmission rate of every 5 seconds with a distance up to 76 meters. The MicroStrain 3-axis accelerometer required an acceleration of 148 mg at 42 Hz, also with a transmission every 5 seconds and a transmission distance up to 76 meters. The Crossbow was powered as low as 290 mg at 18 Hz with a transmission every 60 seconds with a distance up to 30.5 meters. The capacitor profile used during the Crossbow transmissions is shown in Figure 10. A summary plot of the four different sensors and the accelerations used to power them is shown in Figure 11.

VI. CONCLUSION

Using our patented KEH design, various wireless sensors have been powered at low amplitude vibrations based on measured environment vibration levels. These experiments were run as a proof of concept to prove that the design is useful in low-amplitude vibration environments. The harvesters used in these experiments were not optimized for the vibration settings that were used. The vibration spectrum used was also unrealistic compared to what would be expected in a real environment, which has many additional vibrational frequency peaks slightly off the KEH resonance and can vary over time. Depending on the vibration spectrum, it may be desirable to design a harvester with a broader frequency response to capture more of the available energy. The transmission frequency could be lowered to allow more charging time in order to operate at lower vibration amplitudes.

Through our magnetic configuration we have been able to improve upon previous theoretical estimates of potential power harvesters [6]. Future work includes further improvements that can be made to adapt the KEH to a specific environment, enabling them to power wireless sensors and transmitters in an expanding number of environments.

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Figure 9. Charge and discharge of capacitor during TI MSP430 operation

Figure 10. Capacitor profile during Crossbow operation

Figure 11. Four wireless sensors, plotted as the vibration amplitude required to achieve the desired power for transmissions